

Using The Coupling Constant Series to show First Three Interactions are Scalar Multiples

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Abstract:

By using the coupling constant equation in its first representation, i.e. net variations, it is possible to create duality among the first three interactions, exactly at 24+2 variations. Such a duality is in agreement with other theories of GUT. The analysis is done in relatively elegant way using just one equation and the main idea is to vary the net variation in such way that the term would be equal for each element in the series. by performing that procedure on the strong and the electric, the weak interaction gets modified.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

We will take the equation built and first three developments:

$$8 + (1): [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3: [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \quad (2)$$

The idea: we will allow the net variations to vary, and when they have the same value, than the expressions inside the parentheses will become scalar multiple. This will be done by using the idea of virtual variations:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3 \quad (3)$$

Notice that now the third is a scalar multiple of the second by a factor of 5:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

Therefore, the weak and the electric are differing now by a scalar. That is simply beautiful. However, the strong force just accepted that extra two variations so it is just become:

$$8 + (1) + 2 \rightarrow 8 + (1) \quad (4)$$

As Even amounts of variations vanish. It does not affect it. We can try something more interesting, and that is the real purpose of the part:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 2$$

Moreover, the strong just received additional (+3) net variations.

$$8 + (1) + 3 \quad (5)$$

Now this will ruin the duality and the series, the weak and the electric are not isomorphic, and the strong just got a prime amount of variations that cannot vanish. To solve that we can define a virtual exchange of variation $\rightarrow (1\nu)$.

$$[8 + (1)] + 3 - (1\nu): [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3 \quad (6)$$

The real variations are (+3) but to ensure the nature of the strong force, there is a virtual exchange of one variation, marked in color. For a very short time period, the strong is now a scalar multiple of the other two. Overall, they have the same prime amount of net variations – will mean they are at equivalence relation. For the first three forces:

$$N_V = +(3)$$

$$[8 + (1)] + 3 - (1\nu): [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3 \quad (7)$$

We can say that there are three real exchanges and one virtual, so overall four exchanges, which causes all the forces to align on the $N(V) = +(3)$. Taking the average of the Sum: $\frac{4}{2} = 2 \text{ net}$. The converging value of the those exchanges will modify the middle element:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \quad (8)$$

Since we want to keep the prime net variation as it is, to ensure duality, and we can't touch the "invariant" (3), we add this (+2), the first term:

$$((8 * 3) + 2) = 26 \quad (9)$$

The point where they three aligned will be $24 + 2$ variations. certain agreement with this Number exist.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)